

THE CONCEPT OF COMPETITION AND ITS MANIFESTATION IN DIGITAL JOURNALISM

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ABSTRACT

This article talks about the concept of competition, its uniqueness and the concept, place and manifestations of competition in digital journalism.

Keywords: competition, informational market, press, digital journalism, system of media, TCI

INTRODUCTION

The global information market is inherently not a traditional market for goods and services. This is due to the fact that, for political, ideological, cultural and ideological reasons of a strategic nature, it is not characteristic of the classical international division of labor, the content of which is specialization and the accompanying cooperation of the labor of subjects of world economic (information) relations. This means that information competitiveness (information competitiveness) is related to and determined by national competitiveness in general.

New key factors that have a direct impact on the competitiveness in the information space of states in general and professional participants in the information market in particular, in the current conditions of accelerated globalization and the formation of the information society are:

An increase in the amount of available information that exceeds all reasonable limits and biological possibilities of human comprehension. This determines the trends of fragmentation of the information array, the maximum possible simplification and detailing of information in order, on the one hand, to cover the broadest masses, and on the other hand, to create an opportunity for people to quickly and efficiently sort the information flow, that is, the right of the individual to conscious (and unconscious) choice;

Expansion of unlimited access of the masses to any information due to the transboundary nature of information flows, reduction in the cost of information and telecommunication technologies and services that offer more and more advanced channels for instant and high-quality information transfer;

Gradual segmentation of the internal (national) information space into two parallel existing parts - mass (only local analog and sometimes cable television is available; local print media) and elite (global satellite television, news agencies, print publications). Already now, in all countries of the world, without exception, it is obvious that there are two fundamentally different worldviews and models of behavior in society - mass and elite;

Translation of the meaningful part of the information (content) into a format of an entertainment show that is convenient for the masses to perceive, including news, political, social, cultural. At the same time, the intellectual charge of entertainment format content (humor, talk shows, educational programs) is increasing, which tends to become politicized;

METHODS

Consolidation of the Anglo-American (Anglo-Saxon) format as the basic and dominant format of the global and national information space, both in terms of language, thinking and stereotypes, as well as the regulations, mechanisms and tools used. These factors determine the emergence of new threats and challenges, as well as the intensification of competition at all levels of the global information space. In this regard, attention should be paid to the following points:

- the emergence of a trend towards the universalization of culture, worldview, social psychology, stereotypes, which creates favorable conditions for the formation of a global consumer society;
- development of the ideology of multiculturalism and diversity, which erases the boundaries of the principles of national identity;
- weakening the capabilities of the main subjects of the information space to control and regulate the information market;
- involvement of the leading "global players" in aggressive information and propaganda activities in the regional and global information space in order to promote their own interests;
- active introduction of global transnational companies (industry, including energy, and syndicates) into the information market by ordering and financing individual projects and programs, creating their own information divisions,

establishing control over existing professional participants in the information market in order to influence governments and international structures in own interests.

When we talk about the concept of competition itself, we mainly researched it in terms of competition for users' time and attention. However, there is another type of competition that has arisen as a result of the fact that a journalistic product is consumed not only by a trained audience, but also by any inhabitant of our planet. It is common for ordinary people to react not so much to what is better, but to what they like best and to what they are used to. Therefore, in addition to competition of the "faster" and "better" types, there is also competition of the "like it more" or "more convenient to use" type. For example, a high-quality newspaper publication, as you know, is faster, more useful, and more reliable than the tabloid press, which, in turn, is guided not by usefulness, but by interest.

In addition, the media system today is so diverse and accessible, while the news and comments on them are approximately the same and come out with the same frequency, that the competition for "likes more" becomes inevitable both for individual journalists and for a particular mass media.

Digital journalism is also no exception. **Digital journalism**, also known as **netizen journalism** or **online journalism**, is a contemporary form of journalism where editorial content is distributed via the Internet, as opposed to publishing via print or broadcast. What constitutes digital journalism is debated by scholars; however, the primary product of journalism, which is news and features on current affairs, is presented solely or in combination as text, audio, video, or some interactive forms like storytelling stories or newsgames, and disseminated through digital media technology.¹³ Online journalism refers to content created and distributed online. In other words, this is a type of journalism which operates via internet. Online journalism should not be confused with 'citizen journalism'. Online journalism is publishing of information that is equivalent to that of its print and broadcast counterparts (such as newspapers, magazines, radio and television). It follows the professional code of conduct similar to traditional journalism. This is how it differs from citizen journalism, which is not bound by any ethical and professional code of conduct.¹⁴ Digital media is a technology-driven and evolving medium. New innovations, new ideas and concepts are added to it more frequently than in any other traditional media. The introduction of mobile telephony has made access to news a universal phenomenon.¹⁵

¹³ Franklin, Bob (2013). "Digital Journalism", 1:1, p. 1.

¹⁴ <https://egyankosh.ac.in/bitstream/123456789/57137/1/Unit%2011.pdf>

¹⁵ <https://egyankosh.ac.in/bitstream/123456789/57137/1/Unit%2011.pdf>

RESULTS

As noted above, the current large-scale processes that are transforming the media environment are forcing us to rethink the term “journalism” in the new digital conditions. Among these processes:

- firstly, the transition of most traditional media companies to new platforms of the digital environment (in the form of websites and social media accounts);
- secondly, the emergence of new technological tools and text formats in journalistic practices, which radically changed the place of the profession in the information system of society;
- thirdly, new forms of relationships between journalists as authors and the audience as consumers of their texts, leading to the emergence of new hybrid formats and genres.

There are still few examples of the term “digital journalism” entering the academic environment, but they are already noticeable. For several years, the academic journal *Digital Journalism* has been published in Oslo, studying current trends in the development of digital journalism, several English-language monographs have been published that form the field of digital journalism research, conceptualizing and critically comprehending this phenomenon.¹⁶

Digital journalism is the transforming social practice of selecting, interpreting, editing and distributing factual information of perceived public interest to various kinds of audiences in specific, but changing genres and formats. As such, digital journalism both shapes and is shaped by new technologies and platforms, and it is marked by an increasingly symbiotic relationship with the audiences. The actors engaged in this social practice are bound by the structures of social institutions publicly recognized as journalistic Institutions.¹⁷

Fixing the features of digital journalism, almost all authors agree that the most important difference between a professional journalist and the “new professionals” is the principle of responsibility for their texts and for the effects they cause. This is a responsibility to the audience, editors, colleagues, society. It can be emphasized that the need for journalists working in the digital media environment and able to successfully compete with the “new professionals” is found not only at the level of the media industry, but also at the level of society as a whole. Competition is an integral part of this profession. First of all, competition is almost always good for our

¹⁶ Eldridge, Franklin (eds.), 2018; Steensen, Westlund, 2020

¹⁷ What is Digital Journalism Studies?, 2021 Steen Steensen and Oscar Westlund, p 107

development. If consumers had no choice, most important areas of life would simply cease to develop. Competition is a great motivation for improvement, success and professionalism. Through competition, you can become the best in your field. Consider the indicators that most accurately reflect the competitiveness of online media in the media market. An analysis of the modern media market showed that these indicators should include: traffic to the Internet media site, thematic citation index, media citation in users' Internet blogs, compliance of media content with user information requests in search engines.¹⁸

This value allows you to calculate the number of regular site visitors and the dynamics of their visits. The measurement of the above quantitative indicators is available only to the owners of Internet resources. In order to show visitors statistics on the number of visits, the administration of an Internet media site often places a visit counter on the main page. An equally important indicator in the system for evaluating the competitiveness of online media is the thematic citation index (TCI). The citation index is a general designation of numerical indicators that evaluate the popularity of a particular resource, i.e. some absolute value of page importance. The thematic proximity of the resource and the sites referring to it plays an important role. By itself, the number of links to a resource also affects the value of its TCI, but the TCI is determined not by the number of links, but by the sum of their weights. The TIC measurement involves links only from those resources that are indexed in search engines. In fact, the TIC is intended to be an indicator of the assessment of the resource that has developed on the Internet, and not its self-assessment.

Thus, it is not difficult to conclude: the higher the TCI Internet media has, the higher its authority, the more attractive this online publication, and therefore the more competitive. Correspondence of media content to the information needs of users, characterizing the degree of competitiveness of Internet media, for a number of reasons. According to statistics, a large proportion of the audience seeks and finds the necessary information on the Internet using search engines. Thus, the analysis of Internet media website traffic is not able to characterize the true position of the resource in the market: media with high traffic will not always be able to compete with media with a high thematic citation index.¹⁹

DISCUSSION

¹⁸ Формирование конкурентных преимуществ интернет-сми на современном медиа рынке, Белый М.Е. Диссертация на соискание ученой степени кандидата экономических наук ст.29

¹⁹ Формирование конкурентных преимуществ интернет-сми на современном медиа рынке, Белый М.Е. Диссертация на соискание ученой степени кандидата экономических наук ст.35

All factors that ensure the competitiveness of an information product should be divided into three groups:

- factors that ensure the quality of the information product;
- price conditions for access to the information product;
- marketing activity factors

Among the factors that ensure the quality of the information product, we highlight the following:²⁰

1. Content filling. This factor determines the compliance of the materials posted in the Internet media with the information requests of users, as well as their current thematic interests. Information needs depend on the nature and content of a person's activity, their level of education, age, etc.
2. Reliability of information. This factor is of decisive importance in the formation of the image of any media. Many online publications define a high degree of reliability of information and user confidence in it as the main indicators of prestige and respectability.
3. Relevance and selectivity of information. Internet media are constantly updated, and information can change hourly or even minute by minute. We are talking here about the operational coverage of not a specific day, but specific events.
4. Efficiency. This factor can be defined as the duration of the interval between the moment of the event and the moment the message about it appears on the Internet media site.
5. Creativity. The level of creativity of online media is determined by the design of the site, the graphics and colors used, the vocabulary used, grammatical forms and genre specifics. An important element of the online edition is the architecture of the site, its navigation, which makes it possible to simplify the user's access to all information materials posted on the site.
6. Multimedia. Multimedia is commonly understood as the totality of existing textual, illustrative, audio and video technologies. The information capabilities of Internet media increase significantly with the effective use of multimedia technologies.²¹

²⁰ Белый, М.Е. Конкурентоспособность интернет-СМИ на рынке информационных услуг: сборник статей Международной научно-практической конференции «Современный российский менеджмент: состояние, проблемы, развитие» / М.Е. Белый - Пенза, 2005. - С.22.

²¹ Белый, М.Е. Конкурентоспособность интернет-СМИ на рынке информационных услуг: сборник статей Международной научно-практической конференции «Современный российский менеджмент: состояние, проблемы, развитие» / М.Е. Белый - Пенза, 2005. - С.23-24.

CONCLUSION

In digital journalism, as in any field, we can see the concept of competition and its specific characteristics. One of the main causes of competition in digital journalism is obviously reflected in the race to capture users' attention and spend their precious time on their sites. Texts in Internet media should not be too long, because a computer monitor is not an ideal mediator in obtaining information: reading texts from the screen is tiring, and its speed is about 25% slower than reading printed texts. Therefore, journalists engaged with information exchange in the world of the internet today are demanded to provide quick, interesting, reliable, useful and unique information.

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5. <https://egyankosh.ac.in/bitstream/123456789/57137/1/Unit%2011.pdf>
6. What is Digital Journalism Studies?, 2021 Steen Steensen and Oscar Westlund, p 107